

DIFFERENTIATION AND INTEGRATION OF KNOWLEDGE IN THE FORMING OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL – PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF A FUTURE TEACHER OF PHYSICAL TRAINING

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Abstract

The peculiarities of integration and differentiation of knowledge in the forming of the psychological – pedagogical competence of a future teacher of physical training are outlined in the following article. The pedagogical methods of providing differentiation and integration of knowledge and abilities are distinguished and psychological methods in the forming of the psychological – pedagogical competence of future teachers of physical culture are examined in this article.

Key words: *differentiation, integration, knowledge, teacher, physical culture, ways, forming, pedagogical, psychological competence.*

Introduction

The main task of the higher education institute is the training of a specialist for his future professional activity, namely the formation of necessary competence, and one of the means of this formation is the integration and differentiation of subjects.

Integration and differentiation can solve the main task of education - the contradiction between a large amount of knowledge and limited human resources.

Integrated education causes new conditions in the activity of both teachers and students, and is a component of the activation of intellectual activity. It is important to note, that integration and differentiation require innovative forms and methods of education which have a big influence on the effectiveness of the perception of educational material by students. That is why there arises a necessity to determine psychological – pedagogical competence concerning students as future teachers of physical training.

Analysis of research and publication

In scientific works (T. Archipova [2], L. Deminska [4] and others) the question of intersubject contact in the process of the professional training of a teacher is illuminated.

The formation of organizational, communicative, speech and pedagogical abilities of teachers of physical training was investigated by M. Stankin [7], in his scientific works, the determination of the stepwise system of training of teachers of physical training was considered by the following scientists: V. Volkow [4], U. Shkrebtij [9] and others.

The usage of new educational technologies (O. Aksionova [1], A. Chornoshtan [8]) has a great positive influence on the quality of the professional training of future teachers of physical training.

Analysing the psychological – pedagogical literature we have come to the conclusion, that an integrative approach is one of the most determinative in the psychological – pedagogical competence of a future teacher of physical training and requires consideration.

The purpose of the research is to determine peculiarities and meaning of

integration and differentiation of knowledge in forming psychological – pedagogical competence of a future teacher of physical training.

Results of research

The question of the importance of intersubject ties in the process of the formation of psychological – pedagogical competence of future teachers of physical training requires a consistent solution. It is necessary to create optimal conditions in the realization of a professional – pedagogical cycle of discipline [4].

According to V. Volkov the success of a professional activity of a future teacher of physical training is determined by a high level of development of abilities, which requires theoretical knowledge and practical skills. Each of these abilities is concrete and is evaluated only by the professional activity of a teacher of physical training [3].

That is why it is reasonable to use the subject approach to the formation of knowledge of students, which is motivated by the integrative character of training and education process in physical training.

Investigation of the effectiveness in usage of the integrative approach in the process of psychological – pedagogical education of future teachers of physical training results in the renewal of conceptual, theoretical and technical principles, which should meet modern achievements in the sphere of psychology and pedagogics.

The educational process in the higher education establishment should be organized on the principles of humanistic pedagogics, which is oriented towards the development of the personality of a future teacher, able to integrate knowledge, and use it effectively for the purpose of professional self- realization.

It should be noted that reconstruction of the existing system of education is a scientifically grounded integration of knowledge, in close cooperation with its differentiation.

Despite the strengthening of the integrative process at the present stage, the search for cognitive means is becoming widely spread. Together with differentiation, integration plays an important role in the system of physical

education. Differentiation and integration move in opposite directions and at different historical stages one or another method dominates. However, the process of integration and differentiation are subordinated to their own specific laws, performing a function which is specific to each of them within the boundaries of social knowledge [5].

According to our own point of view, educational targets of integration of knowledge should be directed to the formation of integral system of the knowledge of students – future teachers of physical training. The introduction of the integrative process helps to solve a number of important methodical tasks. Interaction of psychological and pedagogical knowledge will give an opportunity to the students to work out the models of psychological – pedagogical situations during the lessons of physical training. Integration of knowledge helps to form the stable competence of a future teacher of physical training necessary for qualitative realization of the educational process concerning physical training in a higher education establishment.

It is important to take into consideration the systematic acquisition of the psychological and pedagogical knowledge of students, their skills in choosing the most effective methods of work for the resolution of model situations. The solution of problems of motivation of knowledge with the help of physical exercises is a necessary condition for the forming of psychological – pedagogical training of a future teacher of physical training.

The integrative approach in physical education is aimed at the realization of main functions namely at formation and the correction of a holistic system of psychological – pedagogical knowledge.

According to our point of view, requirements to the creative thinking of a personality are also very important which are caused by the fact that a majority of practical tasks which a teacher of physical training should constantly decide, require the ability to use psychological-pedagogical knowledge systematically and in an integrated manner: to implicate, combine and systematize a great number of different components of pedagogical and psychological knowledge .

Integration in an educational process, except for specific didactic peculiarities, has general patterns and relationships which exist between scientific knowledge. Consideration of these regularities should be taken into consideration already at the first stages of the forming of psychological – pedagogical competence of students at the faculties of physical training.

All the elements of the integrative system are interconnected and form a certain structure (there can be a number of such systems, depending on the aim of the formation of a system). The main feature of such a system is that the division of an educational material occurs not outside but inside the didactical system.

To ensure continuity and integration of knowledge and skills in the forming of competence of future teachers of physical training, the main pedagogical approaches are identified with the help of defined methods:

- role plays during the lessons of sport games,
- front education during modules in gymnastics,
- circle training during a module of track and field athletics.

Along side this, the ways of forming the psychological competence of a future teacher of physical training are defined, which have the following components:

- group educational activity,
- work in small groups,
- work in pairs,
- methods of autogenic training,
- modeling of "situation of success",
- plot role games,
- psychological components in the evaluation of acquired knowledge by students.

The above proposed psychological and pedagogical ways will help in the effective formation of knowledge and abilities of students necessary for conducting of lessons of physical training in an educational establishment.

Control of the teachers of pedagogics and psychology in collaboration with the worked out models during the practical lessons in sport disciplines will promote deep and wide learning of educational material, which in turn will give the possibility of evaluating the level of pedagogical and psychological competence of students. It will

provide a positive result of work for the future teacher, for the effective conducting of lessons of physical training.

In our opinion, the psychological – pedagogical training of a future teacher of physical training should be carried out on the basis of a method of competence motivated by our specific aims and tasks.

Therefore, the effectiveness of a professional activity of a teacher of physical training depends on the level of competence training. The main factor of success in the professional activity of a teacher of physical training it is an ability to make decisions independently. In the professional activity, prognostication of positive and negative results helps in the educational process of physical training, making proposals to the educational programmes, elaboration of educational – methodical programmes and projects in the process of education in a higher educational establishment.

In our opinion, combining of the integrative approach facilitates the integrity and continuity of a psychological – pedagogical training and of differentiative approach (facilitates the quality of psychological – pedagogical training) and is one of the effective means of the raising of the effectiveness of a psychological – pedagogical training of a future teacher of physical training in a higher educational establishment.

Analysing knowledge and skills of future teachers of physical training, we have come to the conclusion that:

- pedagogical competence of a teacher of physical training lies in the possession of knowledge and skills, the basics of the pedagogics of physical training (aims, principles, context, forms, methods, means of educational activity in a higher educational establishment); means and methods of professional – pedagogical activity; basics of pedagogical skills; by different forms of pedagogical influence on a personality. On the basis of this knowledge: we should use methods of effective organization of activity of pupils in the educational process of a school, analyse educational situations, determine and solve pedagogical problems, conduct analytical research, scientific – pedagogical and practical activity.

- psychological competence of a teacher of physical training is based on possession of knowledge and skills: the main patterns of development of personality: main psychological functions and their psychological arrangements: understanding of the meaning of will and motives and also of unconscious mechanisms in the behavior of a person, age and individual peculiarities of a person: methods of psychological – pedagogical diagnostics in the development of children of different ages and their environment.

On the basis of this knowledge: give the psychological characteristics of a pupil (his temperament, abilities); give the interpretation of his own psychological state; possess the

simplest methods of mental self – regulation; provide psychological aid to pupils; address the psychological impact on pupils, who are in crisis and in conflict situations.

Conclusions

Appliance of integrative and differentiative approach in the formation of psychological competence of students of faculties of physical training promotes more effective assimilation of knowledge and skills concerning psychological – pedagogical disciplines. Application of the given approaches makes it possible to identify ways of creating psychological and pedagogical competence for conducting lessons of physical training.

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